

BUILT 02

Age friendly home

How to make homes safer, more comfortable and easy to maintain for ageing in place

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of Technology

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BUILT

MODULE 2

Age friendly home

In this module, you will learn about the basic features of an age friendly home. It is recommended to consider them when you or someone you know will need some age friendly adjustments to their home.

Introduction

Over the years, our housing needs are changing. When we are very young, a small flat is enough. When we live with a family, we need a larger apartment or a house. When our children leave home, we again no longer need so much space. However, regardless of the phase we are in our lives, the house should be a place where we can live on our terms and where we should feel safe.

It is true that having a place to call home is a basic human need and human right. Therefore, it is essential to shape it appropriately.

Why do we need age friendly homes?

Various studies show that most older people would choose to remain in their current homes. They want to stay in the neighbourhood they are grown into, even though their apartments might not necessarily fully suit their needs. It might also be because they do not have any option of moving into a more suitable apartment.

Fortunately, most people need only minor adjustments to allow them to live independently in older age.

Did you know?

„Ageing in place” is a widely used term nowadays, and it responds to the needs of most older adults.

It is defined as the ability to live safely, independently, and comfortably in one's own home and community, regardless of age, income, or ability level.

Introduction

In this module, you will learn about the basic features of an age-friendly home, which should be:

- Safe
- Functional
- Comfortable
- Easy to maintain

The recommendations provided have a universal character, but you may tailor them to your or your family's needs.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 The importance of safety solutions in the home.
- 2 Functionality as the basis of design decisions.
- 3 How to keep home maintenance costs low.
- 4 Effortless home and the importance of social connectedness.
- 5 Effortless home and the importance of social connectedness.

Chapters in this module

1A safe home

2A functional home

3A comfortable home

4

An easy-to-maintain home

BUILT

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 1

A safe home

Throughout our life, safety at home is very important. However, safety becomes even more important in older age, as older adults spend more time in their homes and often suffer injuries due to hazards.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 The importance of safety at home for the older adult.
- 2 Various hazards at home.
- 3 How to improve safety at home for the older adults.

Safety at home

Research shows that nearly half of all senior citizens' accidents occur in their homes. The most common are falls, which may result in serious injuries.

In this chapter, some general information on safe equipment is first provided.

Safe handling of equipment and facilities

As safety and mobility are strongly linked together, they will be thoroughly presented in the module **BUILT 06: mobility at home.**

Nonetheless, hazards in the homes of older adults are not only linked to mobility. Older people often suffer severe burns caused by gas stoves or hot water running from a tap.

Layout to increase safety

The dwelling layout should limit the need to walk long distances or make many changes of direction on the following routes:

- Bedroom - toilet
- Living room - kitchen
- Living room - entrance area
- Living room - terrace/balcony

Safe mobility

For safe movement, the following are necessary:

- Sufficient space adequate for the mode of movement
- No obstacles (thresholds, carpet edges, cables)
- Stable, non-slippery floor surfaces that make it easy to support oneself.
- Good lighting and contrasting colours of the horizontal and vertical surfaces of furnishings

Safe mobility

The most frequently used equipment and furnishings should be at a height that does not require bending and which is accessible to a sitting or standing person:

- Doorknobs should be placed at 85cm
- Light switches and frequently used objects should be placed at 85-110cm (depending on your height and your preferences)
- Electrical sockets and access to frequently used items (drawers, cupboards) should not be higher than 120cm and not lower than 40cm

Master

ON

OFF

Did you know?

A remote-controlled socket switch is an excellent solution to avoid bending.

A lamp or other appliance plug is plugged into the remote-controlled socket/plug, and you can then control this electrical appliance by using the unit's remote control.

You can learn more about this in Module **SMART 08**.

SMART

Safe mobility

When renovating and furnishing a flat, it is crucial to take into account the risk of mobility impairment, which increases with age:

- each room should have a clear space of 1.5m x 1.5m so that a person who uses a wheelchair would turn around
- Doors width at least 80cm, preferably 90cm
- Corridor passage width at least 120cm

Safe mobility: stairs

Stairs pose a particular challenge, whether a one-family house or an apartment building. Research shows that 85% of accidents with stairs occur at their beginning or end. Therefore, the first and last steps, as well as a platform, should be highly visible. Handrails should be installed preferably on both sides and extend beyond the first and last step.

The lighting of stairs is vital. The spotlights can be installed along the stairs apart from the ambient lamp.

Smart equipment increasing safety

Smart technology is developing rapidly, and it can be very helpful in supporting our safety at home. Here are some examples of simple solutions which everyone can use:

Smoke detector

To install above the stove, depending on the model, it can give sound and light signals when smoke is detected.

Water detector

Important in the bathroom to reduce the risk of flooding

Motion detector

Wireless motion detectors are already widely available on the market. The home will be safer with lighting that switches on when movement is detected.

Safety features of equipment

- Flame-retardant
- Not releasing harmful substances (VOCs, formaldehyde)
- Resistant to damage and, if damage occurs, does not pose a further risk (no glass panes, ceramic elements)
- Reduced injuries resulting from uncontrolled contact with the user (rounded edges, soft surfaces)

Safe entrance

An accessible entrance to the home should be provided, and the front door should have an easily noticeable home number.

Inside the home, the doorbell should be easily heard. The door can be equipped with a smart viewer. It allows us to see who is standing outside and even take a photo of him.

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt about the primary means of enabling safe movement and change of position.

2

You have learnt about smart equipment increasing safety.

3

You have learnt about the safety features of the equipment.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 Providing physical safety at home.

- 2 Safe layout and equipment recommendations.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 2

A functional home

„Form follows function“ is the basic principle of modern design. First, we need to think about the function of a given space and later about its form. Even the most beautiful and expensive solution will not be working unless its functionality is being thought over.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 Functional kitchen.

2 Functional bathroom.

3 Functional bedroom.

A functional home

In this chapter, we will focus on the primary home functions such as: preparing food, hygiene and sleeping.

You will check your kitchen, bathroom and bedroom and see whether these spaces meet your needs.

Functional kitchen

It is estimated that we spend even 40% of the time at home in the kitchen. The more functional it is, the more eagerly we will prepare great meals, which will positively impact our health.

When we are young, we can spend a lot of time standing. But with age, our need for sitting is growing, so it is worth providing a possibility for working in a seated position.

It is also advisable to consider individual needs due to personal physical constraints or design preferences that norms and general recommendations do not reflect.

What is your kitchen like?

Think about your kitchen. Try to answer the following questions:

- Is the size of the kitchen adequate for your needs? (neither too big nor too small)
- Who cooks? How many people?
- Is this your „last” kitchen?
- What kind of things can you do in a kitchen while sitting? Would you like to do more?
- Would you be willing to devote more time in the future to the hobby of cooking?
- Do you think your kitchen is safe? Are there any hazards?
- Do you think you have too many unnecessary kitchen utensils, or would you like to have more?

Worktop adjusted to your height

The worktops used to be at a standard level of 85 cm. However, using too high or too low worktops causes the user to take a very uncomfortable position, resulting in back pains. It is recommended now to adjust the height of the worktop to the main kitchen user height:

- 1.65 m – worktop at 90 cm
- 1.75 m – worktop at 95 cm
- 1.85 m – worktop at 105 cm

What is the height of the worktop in your kitchen? Does it match your size?

Different heights

A table has a height of 71-76 cm. A standard chair is suitable for the table but is not good for the worktop. There are dedicated stools to sit by the worktop available on the market.

Kitchen wall cabinets are mounted 50-60 cm above the worktop. Remember to store heavy items in kitchen cupboards below your shoulder height. Put everything in frequent use at an easily accessible height (basically the first drawer from the top and the first shelf in a cupboard).

The oven should not be installed under the worktop but at a higher level to avoid bending.

The kitchen triangle

The kitchen triangle is formed by:

- Sink
- Refrigerator
- Stove

The distance between them should be min. 40 cm and it should not exceed 210 cm between sink and fridge as well as sink and stove and 270 cm between refrigerator and stove.

Functional kitchen equipment: lightning

Good lighting is essential in the kitchen. It ensures not only a comfortable preparation of the meals but also lowers the risks of injuries. Have a mix of ambient and task lights in your kitchen.

Ambient lighting

Depending on the size of the kitchen, it can be one hanging lamp or more. You can also have several point lights installed on the ceiling.

Under cabinet kitchen lights

LED tapes are a beneficial and safe light source. They do not get hot and are not expensive.

Table lamp

A lamp should be installed 60 cm above the table. Choose a bulb with warm light.

Did you know?

Lumens measure how much light you are getting from a bulb. More lumens means it is a brighter light; fewer lumens means it's a dimmer light.

One lux is equal to one lumen per square meter. It enables us to measure the total “amount” of visible light present and the intensity of the illumination on a surface.

Lux and Lumens

Now, let's look at an example: a kitchen is 3m by 3m giving an area of 9 square metres. In kitchens for older adults, 500 Lux is recommended.

To know how many lumens you need, multiply the Lux by the area. So in this example, 500 Lux x 9 square metres = 4500 Lumens.

These Lumens will be split into several light sources: led tapes over the work top, table lamp and ambient lightning.

The information about the number of lumens is put on a bulb or a Led tape package.

Functional kitchen equipment: storage

Cluttered counters with lots of groceries or kitchen utensils are very unsightly and limit the working space. Remember to keep the most frequently used items in the first drawer and on the first shelf in the hanging cupboard.

Pull cabinets

Install pull cabinets. Various sizes of pull cabinets are available on the market.

Corner base cabinet carousel

Use the corner space for storage by implementing a cabinet carousel.

Drawers

Install drawers instead of traditional kitchen cabinets. They are much more functional. Pay attention to sound quality drawer runners able to carry heavy loads.

Functional kitchen equipment

There are many details to pay attention to when fitting the kitchen. Remember, they should be easy and safe to use.

Kitchen faucet

The kitchen faucet should have a pulldown kitchen sink sprayer. A perfect solution is turning the tap on and off hands-free, not only by limited dexterity

Handy and capacious waste bin

We need to segregate rubbish, which takes a lot of space. Consider this when remodelling your kitchen and try to install a pull-out waste cupboard by touch.

Kitchen handles

Kitchen handles should be well visible and have rounded shapes to minimise the risk of injury.

Functional kitchen - checklist

Now check whether your kitchen is equipped with the following:

- A seat.
- A smoke detector.
- kitchen appliances and cupboards easy to reach.
- Mobility space of 1.5m x1.5m is provided.
- Easy to grip handles.
- Single lever mixer with shower hose.
- A sufficient number of sockets.
- Additional lightning of the worktop and stove.
- The worktop height is good for me.
- Non-slip floor.

Functional bathroom

Next to the kitchen, the sanitary room is the most critical and sensitive home part of all. An older person's independence in this intimate area depends on careful planning.

The bathroom is not only a place for hygienic activities, but also it should be a place for improving wellness and relaxation.

This can be reached when an older person can use the bathroom alone for as long as possible.

What is your bathroom like?

Think about your bathroom. Try to answer the following questions:

- Is the size of your bathroom adequate?
- Do you think your bathroom is safe? Are there any hazards?
- How many people use the bathroom?
- Do you have any difficulties when using your bathroom?
- Do you expect some difficulties to appear in the future?
- Do you have a shower or bathtub, or both? Which one would you prefer?
- Is something missing regarding the equipment of your bathroom?
- Is it possible for you to wash and care for yourself independently?

Bathing

A walk-in shower is the first choice recommendation for an age friendly bathroom. Not only is it safer to use than a bathtub, but it also may not limit the mobility area, which is particularly important for small bathrooms. Modern linear drains allow installation in existing homes even with low spouts (f.ex. Wall models).

The floor in the shower area and the whole bathroom should be made from anti-slippery materials.

Washbasin

The washbasin should be fitted with integrated handles. Pay attention to its quality: the more the washbasin surface is smooth the less dirt will accumulate on it.

It is better not to install drawers underneath to allow for doing some activities on the washbasin being seated.

There should be a possibility to put toiletries and cosmetics nearby.

A mirror that allows you to perform both sitting and standing cosmetic procedures is essential.

Toilet

A toilet should be hung on the level of 46-50 cm, which is higher than recommended for the general population.

A perfect solution is a wash and dry toilet, a combination of a toilet, a bidet and a dryer all in one unit. Not only can a person with mobility issues perform all hygienic activities in one place (reducing the risk of falling while moving from wc to bidet), but it also saves space, which is essential in small bathrooms.

Functional bathroom equipment

There are many details to pay attention to when fitting the bathroom. Remember, everything should be easy and safe to use.

Single faucet with water mixer

Bathroom mixers should be fitted with a heat limiter. They should be easy to use by a person with dexterity limitations

Shower handset and grips

Pay attention to grips and railings and install them when you feel your sense of balance has deteriorated. They should be firmly adjusted to the wall!

A sit

A stool, or as in the above picture, a sturdy cabinet on wheels, where you can store, for example, laundry, are good sitting options for the bathroom.

Functional bathroom - checklist

Now check whether your bathroom is equipped with the following:

- Mobility space of 1.5m x 1.5m is provided.
- Walk-in shower with folding seat or/ and bathtub with safe entry and exit.
- Accessible washbasin.
- A stool to a seat near the washbasin.
- Single-lever mixer tap with burn protection.
- WC height: 46-50cm.
- Horizontal and vertical holding grips near WC, bathtub and shower (if necessary).
- Anti-slip flooring.
- Door width at least 80cm.
- Lighting is suitable for use in damp rooms of at least 300 Lux.
- Bathroom door opening to the outside and unlockable from the outside.

Functional bedroom

Good sleep is necessary to maintain good health, particularly in old age. To enjoy a good quality sleep, we should pay attention to our bedroom and its adequate equipment.

Older adults may need to spend more time in bed due to some health issues. A functional bedroom may positively influence their recovery.

What is your bedroom like?

Think about your bedroom. Try to answer the following questions:

- Does something need to be changed or is it perfectly fine?
- Can you sleep well in your bedroom?
- Would you like to sleep separately from your partner (because, for example, he snores, and it wakes you up, or you snore, and your partner cannot sleep well, you have a different sleep rhythm, etc.)? Remember that sleep quality is essential for staying healthy!
- Are there any sleep disturbances in your bedroom?
- Is there enough light? Can you read in bed?
- Is there enough storage opportunities?

A bed

First of all, you need the right bed. Standard beds have a low platform, but in older age, it is much easier to get in and out of a bed that has some considerable height.

A bed's height should not be less than 60 cm. It can be higher if you are a tall person.

To lean back comfortably, soft bed headrests are worth considering.

You can also think about an electric adjustable bed frame which may be helpful by i.e. problems with swelling legs.

Functional bedroom

Illumination is also essential in a bedroom. The windows should be equipped with blackout curtains. There are solutions available on the market that allow the remote control to open and close the curtains.

Artificial lighting is equally important. Provide bed lights to be able to read in bed.

A motion-activated skirting board or motion-activated led lights (completely wireless, fuelled with AAA batteries, can be placed everywhere) are recommended for night walking. The recommended lux number is 300.

Functional bedroom - checklist

Now check whether your bedroom is equipped with the following:

- Bed at least 60cm high.
- Technical devices (light switches) to control and have control over the bed's environment are next to the bed.
- A bedside table to store medications, glasses etc.
- Mobility space of 1.5m x1.5m is provided.
- Reading lamps.
- Bathroom is close to the bedroom.
- Motion sensor lights leading to a bathroom are installed.

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt about the functional kitchen features.

2

You have learnt about the functional bathroom features.

3

You have learnt about the functional bedroom features.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 Functionality is the key to good design.

- 2 You know three basic home functions.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 3

A comfortable home

Comfort is vital for our physical, social and mental well-being. In this chapter, we shall take a look at what we can do to improve comfort in our homes and particularly in homes of older adults.

Comfort at home

In this chapter, we shall take a closer look at some different types of comfort that our homes should provide for us:

- acoustic comfort
- visual comfort
- thermal comfort
- olfactory comfort and air quality

Notice that these types of comfort refer to our senses and highly influence our physical, mental, and social well-being.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Acoustic comfort.
- 2 Visual comfort.
- 3 Thermal comfort.
- 4 Olfactory comfort and air quality.

Acoustic comfort

For most of us, the senses weaken with age. We tend to have a poorer vision and more difficulties with mobility. This also relates to hearing. However, even though many older adults will have problems with hearing, some may also become more susceptible to certain noises, which can irritate them. This can occur particularly for people who have dementia or other neurological disorders. The cry of a baby or a dog barking can be very uncomfortable for these people.

Acoustic comfort

Therefore, it is crucial to reduce the noise from outside the building by, for example, providing tight-fitting windows, which can be helpful, particularly during the winter.

Equally significant is the reduction of noise from other dwellings or apartments in the building. Reducing noise in existing buildings is pretty difficult, but many countries' regulations impose appropriate standards for new buildings.

Did you know?

In the city, traffic is the primary source of noise.

Noise levels of 35 dB to 70 dB begin to hurt our nervous system (symptoms are fatigue, reduced efficiency, and difficulty sleeping). Such noise impedes communication. Staying in sustained noise of 70 - 85 dB causes permanent hearing deterioration, headaches and nervous disorders.

Acoustic comfort

We should also pay attention to household appliances so they do not emit noise or other sounds, particularly at night.

For example, if ventilation systems are not given adequate care, they may become very loud.

Acoustic comfort

You can also introduce some solutions which improve acoustic comfort at home. Generally, soft surfaces absorb sound, while hard ones reflect it and increase reverberation. That is why it is good to have some curtains or carpets. Special acoustic panels installed on walls are also available on the market.

An older person who watches TV at a high volume may not necessarily have serious hearing problems. Poor acoustics in a room caused by high reverberation might lead to hearing difficulties.

Visual comfort

Visual comfort is primarily ensured by:

- Adequate lighting
- Colours (enhancing contrast)
- Window view

You already know how many lux you need in your home.

However, there is also another unit describing light: Kelvin. It relates to the temperature of light, which can be warmer or colder. A warm colour temperature is typically 3.000K or less. You can find this information on the bulb or led tape package. It is recommended to use warm light in an age-friendly home.

Did you know?

The morning sunlight is cold and intense. It stimulates the cortisol secretion in our bodies, making us awaken and ready to act.

In the evening, the sunlight is warmer and less intense. It induces the production of melatonin, which is the hormone that is necessary for good sleep.

Visual comfort

A day room should get sufficient sunshine during the day.

Visual comfort requires appropriate insolation. As you will learn from the module **BUILT 05**, sufficient daylight is necessary to keep us in good health.

Bearing in mind the ongoing effects of climate change, it is essential to provide shades or shutters to protect us from excess sunshine in case of a heat wave.

Visual comfort – enjoy the colour!

A common misconception is that older adults like to have only white walls. Research shows that they prefer coloured walls.

As a result, older adults' homes look quite similarly: white walls and dark (black, grey or brown) furniture.

However, white walls may worsen depression symptoms, give little recognisability, and are simply boring.

Colours can also positively impact our mood. You can influence it by choosing between warm (energising) and cold (calming) colours.

The power of colours: cold and warm

Green

Brings a sense of calmness and security

Yellow

Energizes, adds brightness

Blue

Creates quiet, relaxing atmosphere

Orange

It is linked with happiness, energy and creativity

Visual comfort

You may have rooms painted in different colours. Most of the walls may remain white, while only selected (for example, well-lit wall in a day room) may be painted with colour.

Colour choice

Do not hurry when choosing a colour for a wall. Use a paint sample on a wall and wait a couple of days. Make sure you like it.

Colourful ceiling – why not?

You may paint with colour a ceiling and leave the walls white. This is a good solution in narrow rooms.

Increase contrast

You can play with contrast: white switches on a darker wall and black switches on a white border.

Thermal comfort

With age, we tend to become more and more sensitive to temperature variations. Even a drop or increase of two degrees may be uncomfortable for older adults.

Therefore, ensuring no significant temperature differences within the dwelling is essential in an age friendly home.

This can be challenging when the house is big, or some rooms are north-facing while others are south-facing.

Thermal comfort

Ensuring thermal comfort in the wintertime is very challenging for many older adults because many of them cannot afford sufficient heating. This is a problem for many seniors, particularly in central and northern European countries.

The possibility to adjust the temperature to one's needs should be provided, and it should be independent of the general building system (in multi-family housing).

Thermal comfort

With the progression of climate change, more and more seniors will experience health problems caused by heat waves. Therefore, it is recommended to install air-conditioning appliances in age friendly homes.

The air-conditioning should be equipped with a humidifier as cooled air is arid, which can negatively impact an older person's health.

The air-conditioning appliance should also be regularly checked to avoid a build up of fungus/ or dampness.

Olfactory comfort

Excessively strong or distinct odours can disrupt physical and psychological well-being and even trigger eye, nose, and throat irritation, nausea, and headaches. This can come from, for example, VOC and formaldehyde emissions from finishing materials. That's why it is recommended to buy wall paints with certificates proving that they are health friendly.

Olfactory comfort - kitchen

The kitchen may sometimes be a source of unpleasant smells. Therefore, it is essential to install an efficient hood in a kitchen, which is easy to operate by an older person. When choosing the kitchen hood, pay attention to its noisiness. Some models may be loud.

Air quality comfort

Many older adults suffer from asthma and allergies. The more pollution in the air, the more severe symptoms they have.

The pollution may come from the outside, through the windows or ventilation. It can also derive from daily use or home pets.

We can install ventilation system filters, which need to be regularly checked. Moreover, air purifiers are available on the market. They are beneficial, particularly for those with an allergy, because they remove pollen from the air.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 2** | **CHAPTER 3**

What does Kelvin unit describe?

- light temperature
- light intensity

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt about different types of comfort in an age friendly home.

2

You have learnt about possibilities to enhance each type of comfort in the home.

3

You have learnt about the importance of comfort for our health.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1** You know why comfort is important.

- 2** You know what comfort is needed.

- 3** You know how to ensure comfort.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 4

Easy to maintain home

An age friendly home should be easy to maintain in the financial, physical and social senses. Let's see in detail what this means.

Easy to maintain home

An age friendly home should be easy to maintain in a financial, physical, and social sense.

This is very important as, with age, we lose financial resources and physical strength and tend to rely more on others.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 Financial maintenance.

2 Physical maintenance.

3 Social maintenance.

Financial maintenance

As we get older, our limited income may make it difficult to pay for housing or to ensure adequate comfort, e.g. a comfortable temperature.

Thermal insulation can help to lower heating costs. Energy may be saved by using energy-efficient appliances.

Sometimes it might help to move to a smaller house or apartment. Another possible option is to share the home and bills with someone.

Heating

Heating poses one of the most significant expenses, which may be particularly challenging for older adults.

Do not overheat your home

WHO recommends keeping 21 C degrees in a day room and 18 degrees in the other occupied rooms.

Install smart radiator thermostat

It can keep the temperature of a room on the desired level without overheating. It can also be programmed not to heat at i.e. night.

And control heating

If you are familiar with smart technologies, you may use an application which allows you to control heating when you are away.

Other saving opportunities

There are many small measures which can help you reduce home costs.

Faucets with aerators

The aerator adds air to the water flowing through the faucet and reduces the amount of water flow. All modern faucets are equipped with aerators. But if you have an older type, you may add an aerator to it.

Maybe a smaller fridge?

Think about whether you need a large fridge. Maybe a smaller one would fit your needs. The energy expenses could be lower.

Vinyl panels

When renovating your home, pay attention to new and affordable materials. Instead of traditional tiles in a bathroom or kitchen, you can install vinyl panels, a more affordable option.

Cheaper renovation

You may try to reduce the renovation costs and here are some ideas which you can use:

Paint existing tiles

If tiles fit well to the wall, but you do not like the colour anymore, do not remove them but paint them. Many paint producers offer products for tiles painting.

Tiling over tiles

Removing old tiles is very costly. But it is possible to glue new tiles on top of old ones. This is good in the shower area as tiles painting is not recommended there.

Selected application

Easily washable paints are expensive. But you may use them just on some parts of walls which can get easily dirty. A wainscoting might be an excellent outcome.

People living in under-occupied dwellings, by age class, 2018

(%)

Did you know?

Older adults in Europe live in different conditions. For example, Irish seniors often live in (large) family houses with gardens, while Polish seniors tend to have smaller homes, usually apartments.

Therefore, it is impossible to make a universal recommendation for an appropriate age friendly home size. It depends mainly on the local conditions and cultural determinants.

Physical maintenance

Cleaning becomes more and more tedious with age. Therefore, uniform finishing materials with washable surfaces should be provided. Storage areas should be kept closed, to avoid dust accumulation.

Physical maintainance

Broad band is a must

Not only allows it to connect with others but also smart home facilities may be used

Entertainment center

A TV set connected to Internet may be an entertainment centre to enjoy alone or with friends and relatives

Fuses at an accessible height
Fuses are often installed in a hardly accessible location. Make sure you can reach them.

Social maintenance

An age friendly home should have access to services, public transport and the Internet. Facilities like this make socialising and maintaining contact with family and friends easier.

To be able to stay in familiar surroundings for as long as possible, it is essential that:

- your home is appropriately equipped
- the living environment is appropriate for your needs
- appropriate help and social networks are available in the environment

Chapter summary

1

You have learnt about an age friendly home's financial, physical and social maintenance.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

How to maintain an age friendly home financially.

2

How to maintain an age friendly home physically.

3

How to maintain an age friendly home socially.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Module summary

1

You have learnt about safety in an age friendly home.

2

You have learnt about different comforts in an age friendly home.

3

You have learnt about functionality in an age friendly home.

4

You have learnt about maintaining an age friendly home.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 You know what an age friendly home is.

- 2 You know what to do to create one.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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